

Zulip Quick Start Guide

Make the most of Zulip – in 3 key ways

By: Samantha Wittke (CSC-IT Center for Science), Danny Garside (Digital Research Academy), Katie Pratt (CSCCE), and Lou Woodley (CSCCE)

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About the guide

This Quick Start Guide is a template that can be used by anyone running a Zulip community to help orient new members as they get started. It can be adapted to meet your needs under a CC BY license. From here onwards, it is written from the perspective of a community manager speaking to their members.

If you're new to Zulip, or simply overwhelmed by the prospect of yet another community group, here are some quick tips to help you to configure and use the tool in a way that works best for you. They are organized into 3 key areas:

1. Configuring your account
2. Adjusting the volume – channels, topics, and notification settings
3. Communicating with others

Any questions? Visit the [Zulip help center](#), or email <your community contact email address>.

Note: these instructions are created for the browser version of Zulip. There are also [desktop and mobile apps](#) that may have minor differences.

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CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

SAMANTHA WITTKÉ - Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

DANNY GARSIDE - Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

KATIE PRATT - Supervision, Visualization, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

LOU WOODLEY - Writing - Reviewing and Editing

Citing and reusing this guide

CITATION AND REUSE

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1. Configuring your account

A. PROFILE

When you set up your profile there are several things to bear in mind:

- **Your name** – Please use a name by which others will be able to identify you. This is separate from your email address, which will not be visible to other users (your email address will only be visible to workspace admins).
- **Your avatar** – Please add a profile picture or other identifier that you're comfortable with so that others can associate your posts with you more easily.
- **Your time zone** – This determines when Zulip will notify you and can also help others know whether it's a reasonable time of day to get in touch.
- **Your pronouns** – You can choose to share your pronouns.
- **Your affiliation** – Please add your role and the community that you're working with to help others get to know you.
- **Your bio** – You can add additional information about yourself here.

To update your profile, click your avatar in the top right of the screen and select "View your profile" and then select the edit icon at the top of the profile card. Profile edits are saved automatically – there's no "Save" button to click.

When you hover over another member's avatar in Zulip you're invited to "View user card," which contains information such as when they were last seen in the community and their status. You also have the option to click through from the card to see their full profile (which can be [customized at the admin level](#) to include additional profile fields, such as ORCID or GitHub).

B. YOUR VISIBILITY

You can control various aspects of how visible your presence and your activity is on Zulip:

- Click the gear icon next to your avatar at the top right of the page.
- Select "Personal Settings" then "Account and Privacy."
- Here you can:
 - Determine whether others can see that you have read content,
 - Determine whether to display your availability,
 - Let administrators export your private data,
 - ...and more!

C. STATUS UPDATES

Status updates can be a useful way to let others know your availability. For example, if you're away at a conference, you may want to let others know that you'll be slower to respond or entirely absent from the group.

Remember that your status will be visible to everyone in the Zulip group.

To update your status, click your avatar in the top right of the screen and type your status.

You can clear a status update at any time by clicking the "x" icon next to your status.

2. Adjusting the volume – channels, topics, and notification settings

A. HOW TO FIND AND JOIN CHANNELS

The default channels in Zulip are defined by you and other organization owners. This may include some welcome/greetings channels, as well as other channels that are of common interest.

To find additional channels:

- Click the gear symbol next to your profile picture in the upper right corner.
- Choose "channel settings."
- You will initially see all channels you are subscribed to (if you would like to see all **available** channels in the workspace, change the view in the upper left from "subscribed" to "available").
- Click on a channel in the list to view more information.
- You can subscribe yourself to the channels you are interested in by clicking "subscribe" in the top right corner (or by clicking the "+" icon to the left of the channel name in the channels list).
- Once you have joined a channel it will be listed in the left sidebar,
- Click a channel name to load the channel in the center pane.

You're welcome to join any public channel within the workspace.

B. HOW TO START A CONVERSATION

- **To send a message in Zulip**, click on a channel in the left sidebar and then choose the topic you'd like to contribute to. Clicking on the topic will make a window appear at the bottom of your screen into which you can type your message.
- If there is no suitable topic available for the conversation you would like to have (or you can't find one), **start a new topic** by clicking the "+" to the right of the channel name in the left sidebar.
- **Messages can be moved between topics and channels** if you find out later that your message would actually fit in another topic/channel. To do this click on the three dots (aka the "kebab" menu) either at the topic or the message level and choose "Move topic" or "Move messages."
- If your new message fits an existing topic, use that topic to **continue conversations**. You can also "Mark as unresolved" a previously "resolved" topic, if that seems appropriate. To do this, click the kebab menu next to the topic title and select "Mark as unresolved."

C. ORGANIZING YOUR CHANNELS

- Once you've joined all the channels you're interested in, you can pin the channels you use the most to the **Pinned Channels** section.
- To do this, click the kebab menu next to the channel name in the left sidebar and select "Pin channel to top."
- Your workspace admin can also set up **folders to organize channels** in the left sidebar, and you can choose to "group channels by folder" by clicking the kebab menu.
- If you would like to request a new folder, please contact <your workspace admin>.

D. VIEWS

Zulip provides multiple ways to view your conversations, listed in the Views section of the sidebar:

- **Inbox** shows how many new additions to topics/direct messages since you last checked in.
- **Recent conversations** gives you an overview of new messages, with the most recent activity at the top (note: at the top of this view, you can choose to filter by conversations that are "unread" or that you've "participated" in, as well as whether to include DMs).

- **Combined feed** shows all messages in chronological order (except those in channels and topics you have muted).
- **Mentions** shows all of your messages that have received any emoji reactions.
- **Reactions** includes all messages that mention your username (note: if your workspace is configured to support groups, any messages sent to a group you are part of will also show up here).
- **Starred messages** are messages that you have chosen to flag as important.
- **Drafts** includes messages you haven't sent yet.

E. CONFIGURING YOUR NOTIFICATIONS

Zulip has lots of options for you to determine how and when you want to be informed about content – and at what level of granularity.

i) For the overall organization

- Click on the gear icon next to your avatar at the top right of the page and select “personal settings” from the dropdown.
- In the Notifications section you have options, which include:
 - Enable visual and audible desktop, mobile, e-mail notifications.
 - Choose to be alerted when certain keywords are mentioned or certain channels or topics have any activity.

ii) Channel by channel

- When you're in a channel, open the drop-down menu by clicking on the kebab menu next to the channel name.
- You can either mute the channel directly or go to channel settings to change notifications under “personal.”
 - Here you have the option to ignore any @all messages, set notifications for desktop/mobile/e-mail, or mute the channel entirely.

iii) Following a specific topic

- In addition to full channels, you can also choose notification settings for individual topics.
- Click on the kebab menu next to the topic name to change your notification settings.
- You can choose between “mute,” “default,” and “follow.”
- Your choices here may also affect how messages in this topic show up in different views.

F. OTHER WAYS TO LIMIT NOISE

If a topic is no longer active or of interest, it can be “resolved” to indicate this to anyone finding the topic later.

Alternatively, if a channel or topic has become too noisy, you can:

- **Mute it:** Within the channel, open the drop-down menu by clicking on the kebab menu next to the channel name and select “Mute channel” from the “notifications” dropdown.
- **Unsubscribe:** Within the channel, open the drop-down menu by clicking on the channel name at the top of the pane in the list on left and select “unsubscribe” from the menu.

3. Communicating with others

A. A FEW POINTS OF ETIQUETTE

- To add a reply to a topic, click the last message in the topic to show the edit box to type your message.
- You can answer a specific message, by “quoting” that message (click the kebab menu next to the message “quote message”, the text will be added to the edit box and you can add your text).
- Use @all sparingly:
 - If you type @all in a post or comment that will send a notification to everyone in that channel – please use this only for items that really do need everyone’s attention.
 - You can notify one person by using @username in your message.
 - How users get notified about these mentions depends on their settings.
- Respect the context of the shared space: While this group is open for anyone interested in <insert your community’s interests>, we want it to be somewhere where learning can happen in a supportive, safe environment.
- We suggest that you do not take conversations out of context and copy/paste them elsewhere without the permission of all the individuals who posted.

B. SENDING PRIVATE MESSAGES

It can be helpful to others when you're sharing resources and brainstorming solutions to "work out loud" in a specific thread, because then your learning becomes a future resource for others too.

However, sometimes you want to start a private conversation. To do this, click on a person's profile image and choose "Send a direct message." This will open a private thread for you to talk to each other. You can also add additional recipients to a DM to create a small group thread.

That's it – you're good to go!